

PERCEPTION OF TELECOMMUNICATION USAGE IN THE FIGHT AGAINST INSECURITY: A CASE OF DEFENCE AND SECURITY STUDIES CLASS, NIGERIAN DEFENCE ACADEMY KADUNA

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Abstract: Technology plays a crucial role in the ongoing fight against insecurity such as terrorism, insurgency, abduction, robbery, and cyber security worldwide, particularly in Nigeria as such, the investigated the perception of telecommunication in the fight against security in the Defence and Security Department, NDA, Kaduna and to recommend other security measures that can be adopted to improve the security issues in the Defence and Security Department, NDA, Kaduna. Hybrid methodology was adopted in the research where questionnaires were used to gather information from participants and Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS) was used to analyse collected data. The findings of the research show that the use of telecommunication gadgets has no effect in improving security in NDA at an average cumulative mean value of 2.71 which is lower and below the acceptable mean value of 3.0. The research concludes that the expense of countering security is high, the stress on the operator is high, and the potential for loss of life is high as most anti-security tools of today are high-tech, pricey, and need a high level of technical expertise to use effectively as such, technology is the driving force behind the struggle against security. The study recommends that legislation mandating the long-term, cost-effective acquisition of crime-fighting equipment has to be officially promulgated by the Federal Government of Nigeria. To that end, the Nigerian security force would be supplied with the latest technological advances regularly.

Keywords: Perception, Telecommunication, Fight against Security and Defence and Security.

1. INTRODUCTION

Securities such as robbery, abduction, terrorism, and insurgency in Nigeria have become more complex and widespread as criminal groups have turned to high-tech methods, such as the use of mobile phones and the internet, to exploit and unleash their illegal operations on the public (Adigun, Raimi & Mutiu, 2020). According to Ogu and Oyerinde (2014), Nigeria is third on the list of nations most often linked to reported cyber security incidents, based on data from the 2008 report of Cyber Security's Complaints from the Online Crime Complaint Centre (IC3), an organisation set up to investigate internet security.

A technologically driven security industry is essential to achieving long-term safety on a global scale. Increasing safety requires the use of cutting-edge technology (Marije, 2013). Current technological development is altering international security structures. There has been a worldwide use of the science and art of critical information collection in the ongoing

effort to reduce crime rates. This is because technology has made modern security possible. The global security industry is up against unprecedented problems, including the need to fight security's shifting nature and scale, handle the growing threats presented by transnational criminal networks, and cope with the ever-present danger of international and domestic terrorism. Also, they have to keep up with the rising public demand for safety measures. Technology plays a crucial role in the ongoing fight against terrorism, insurgency, abduction, robbery, and cyber security worldwide, particularly in Nigeria.

This is why Daly (2003) contends that using technology, particularly in the field of information management, to combat security will not be successful via force. In addition, he argues that the security forces' physical capabilities have been overvalued in the war on crime. In contrast, in most emerging nations, nothing has been done to locate the foes on a borderless battlefield. Since criminals in Nigeria don't have a defined playing field, we need a reliable and regularly updated criminal data repository to profile them and their actions. These spawned the development of communication technologies, including telegraphy, telephones, radio waves, copper wires, and face-to-face interactions. From the early 20th century to the present day, people have worked hard to create better technologies that may help them provide a high level of service with sufficient facilities and services to keep up with the demands of the times (Ige, 2002).

This incredible rate of technological development has opened up a wealth of possibilities for the free flow of data throughout any country's manufacturing and service industries. Information and communication technology have altered the way governments throughout the world function. Since the late 1990s, digital cameras have been put on highways in advanced nations to identify traffic regulation infractions, most notably speeding, according to Howells (2018). Many of these progressive nations have only lately adopted police body cams. Security services also face new challenges due to the evolving nature of security in the digital era, such as public disturbances, shoplifting, domestic violence, robbery (on the street, in homes, and banks), abduction, and terrorism. Security detection and countermeasures are an alternative regulation method. Biometric technologies such as fingerprint readers, DNA sequencers, and voice recognition systems are only some of the many tools used for security detection (Alzubai & Kalta, 2016). According to Johnny (2020), security operators can better analyse satellite photos for surveillance and criminal identification thanks to artificial intelligence (AI). The rapid advancement of technology has opened up new vistas for communication, increased efficiency, and boosted growth, but it has also influenced a sea change in criminal behaviour. Some criminals exploit cutting-edge technology, making previously effective security measures obsolete. In Nigeria, this has led to a rise in security incidents, which the country's current security system is ill-equipped to address (Adigun, Mutiu & Raimi, 2020). As a result of technology's growing influence on the conduct of crime in Nigeria, cutting-edge tools must be used in the pursuit of security in keeping with international best practices.

This study analyses the role of telecommunications devices in enhancing security in the defence and security class at the Nigerian Defence Academy in Kaduna and compares the results to the current state of security in the country and the poor performance of security personnel in preventing, detecting, and countering security in Nigeria.

Statement of the Problem

There has been a shift in criminal activity both internationally and in Nigeria. These crimes, like the environment they inhabit, are always evolving in response to new technologies. The nation faces a wide variety of security threats, including but not limited to theft, armed robbery, abduction, and acts of terrorism. There is no doubt that Nigeria is suffering security issues, as stated by Osibanjo (Ajasa, 2021). The government of Nigeria has been working around the clock to provide its residents with the best possible protection. Although there have been reforms to the security sector, the security services in Nigeria still have not been able to provide enough protection for the country. Numerous researchers have compiled mountains of data to find answers to Nigeria's security problems.

Many experts have conducted extensive research to address Nigeria's security issues. Studies on community policing as a strategic security development in Nigeria were undertaken by Fatile, Adejuwon, and Bello (2018), and Omonu (2018) titled "Police training of senior officers: An essential to performance enhancement" Attempt a qualitative investigation of the significance of NPF training for enhanced performance. However, Howells (2018) researched to investigate the role of technology in modern crime prevention. None of the aforementioned research appears to have shown a connection between technological vitality and efficient crime prevention in Nigeria. This research addresses a need that has been noted in the existing literature.

Research Questions

The study will be guided by the following research questions

- i. What are the effects of telecommunication in the fight against security in the Defence and Security Department, NDA, Kaduna?
- ii. What are the challenges militating against the effective usage of telecommunication in the fight against security in the Defence and Security Department, NDA, Kaduna?
- iii. What other security measures can be adopted to improve the security issues in the Defence and Security Department, NDA, Kaduna?

Objectives of the Study

The following objectives will be achieved at the end of the study

- i. To examine the effects of telecommunication in the fight against security in the Defence and Security Department, NDA, Kaduna.
- ii. To examine the challenges militating against the effective usage of telecommunication in the fight against security in the Defence and Security Department, NDA, Kaduna.
- iii. To recommend other security measures that can be adopted to improve the security issues in the Defence and Security Department, NDA, Kaduna.

2. METHODOLOGY

Research Design

Instead of conducting a large statistical survey or in-depth comparative analysis, a case study method instead narrows down on a single research issue and examines it in great depth. This study employs both quantitative and qualitative methods, which increases the trustworthiness and validity of the findings. Quantitative research strategies are appropriate, especially when applied to a larger population and gathering quantitative data, whereas qualitative techniques supply descriptive data to define study concerns. This research strategy is utilised to shed light on a murky topic by in-depth analysis of a select set of related instances or contexts. To learn more about telecommunication usage in the fight against insecurity, several quantitative methods were used to better understand the qualitative study's results and, perhaps, provide a wiser interpretation of those findings.

Researchers that adhere to interpretivism, as argued by Mertens (2019), assign meaning to their findings as interpretivism takes into account the human dimension of a research project. Therefore, interpretative academics hold the view that only via social inventions like language, consciousness, shared meanings, and instruments can one get access to reality (whether given or socially constructed). Interpretivism is a philosophical school that originated as a response to positivism within the social sciences and which continues to question positivist assumptions. As a social actor, the interpretivist researcher values differences among study participants (Saunders et al., 2019). Moreover, interpretivism research often zeroes on the meaning and may use a variety of methods to mirror the many elements of the issue. Due to the researcher's desire to interact with her subjects and get a more nuanced understanding of their perspectives via the unique application of interpretation and intervention in a fully comprehensible reality, the interpretive research technique was used here.

Instruments of Data Collection

Primary and secondary data sources are two types of data-gathering techniques that are crucial to any study strategy. A structured, self-administered questionnaire developed by the researcher as a mode of data collection. The questionnaire comprises of three sections, White and McBurney (2022) note that researchers should consider the study's budget, time constraints, the necessary level of precision, researcher experience, and other factors when deciding which data-collecting technique to use. Researchers utilised questionnaires to gather information from participants. A questionnaire, as described by Bougie and Sekaran (2019), consists of a collection of preformulated textual questions to which respondents record replies, often within very narrowly defined alternative options. Rahi (2017) argues that questionnaires are primarily used to obtain numerical data in huge quantities. The researcher developed a comprehensive questionnaire with many parts; some portions were directed by the study's aims, while others featured demographic components where respondents described

their characteristics. Respondents were asked to fill out the surveys in person, which allowed the researcher to quickly amass a representative sample of the population's opinions.

Data Analysis Technique

When data collection is complete, the next step is analysis to make the data more easily interpretable. Data analysis also aids in determining whether or not the study's aims were successful (Nachmias & Nachmias, 2015). The researcher double-checked the raw data they gathered afterwards to make sure no mistakes were made. The data were also analysed by the researcher to look for mistakes and gaps that would need to be filled up. The researcher coded the data and entered it into Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS) after fixing the mistakes and exclusions. The numbers were run through SPSS and got some nice tables with percentages and such.

Descriptive statistics, including means and percentages, were used to summarise survey results and star ratings. The existing link between the variables was evaluated using inferential statistics. Strategic planning (the independent variable) was correlated with the growth of small and medium-sized enterprises (the dependent variable) to identify influential elements in both areas.

3. PRESENTATION AND ANALYSIS OF RESULTS

All 15 questionnaires were sent out to the sample group, and 15 were filled out and returned. This amounted to a response rate of 100% and was enough for the study.

Table 1: Respondents' Response Rate

Category	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Distributed	15	100
Responded	15	100
Did not Respond	0	0
Total	15	100

Gender Respondents

The researcher sought to determine the gender distribution of the population and the results presented in Figure 1 indicate that 10 (66%) were male, and 5 (33%) were female. These results show that more males run defence and security programs compared to females, this could be a result of the nature of the industry.

Figure 1: Gender Respondents

Quantitative Analyses

The respondents were asked to rate several questions on telecommunication usage in combating insecurity in NDA adopting the scale of 1-Strongly Disagree, 2-Disagree, 3 - Neutral, 4-Agree, and 5-Strongly Agree. The results were as presented in Table 2. Table 2 shows that NDA has not reaped the benefits of telecommunication in fighting insecurity with a mean value

of 2.27; insecurity is not overcome in NDA using telecommunication indicating 2.33 mean value; also not deal of time and devotion is given to the fight of insecurity in the NDA at 2.07 mean value; at not point does ideas were exchanged on insecurity with other security operatives on the use of telecommunication indicating 1.95 mean value; this made respondents to agree that telecommunication does not have any effect on the fight for insecurity in NDA at 4.07 mean value; the table further shows that NDA has no telecommunication capacity to fight insecurity at 3.47 mean value; also that whenever new telecommunication technique is been introduced, NDA always dejected it which indicated 3.40 mean value; but then the respondents expectations are not encouraged when security matters are been discussed with other security agents at 2.40 mean value even when there is synergy on the nature of the relationship among telecommunication users and the various security agencies at 2.93 mean value and lastly, there is no satisfaction with the security measures placed in the NDA for fight against insecurity this indicated 2.27 mean value. Generally, the use of telecommunication gadgets has no effect in improving security in NDA at an average cumulative mean value of 2.71 which is lower and below the acceptable mean value of 3.0.

Table 2: Rating of Use of Telecommunication in Combating Insecurity

S/NO.	STATEMENTS	MEAN	DECISION
1	The NDA has reaped the benefits of telecommunication in fighting insecurity.	2.27	Disagreed
2	With the help of telecommunication, insecurity is overcome in NDA.	2.33	Disagreed
3	A deal of time and devotion is given to the fight against insecurity in the NDA.	2.07	Disagreed
4	Ideas are been exchanged on insecurity with other security operatives on the use of telecommunication.	1.93	Disagreed
5	For me, telecommunication does not have any effect on the fight against insecurity in NDA.	4.07	Agreed
6	NDA has no telecommunication capacity to fight insecurity.	3.47	Agreed
7	Whenever a new telecommunication technique is been introduced, NDA always dejected it.	3.40	Agreed
8	My expectations are so high when security matters are been discussed with other security agents that they frequently divert the subject matter from the tasks at hand.	2.40	Disagreed
9	There is no synergy like the relationship between telecommunication users and the various security agencies.	2.93	Disagreed
10	Generally speaking, I am satisfied with the security measures placed in the NDA for the fight against insecurity.	2.27	Disagreed
	Cumulative Mean	2.71	Disagreed

4. DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

Taking the defence and security class at Nigeria's Defence Academy (NDA) as a case study, this research looked at the role that technology (telecommunication) plays in the battle over security. The introduction of ICT in the second part of the 20th century had a profound effect on people's social lives, economic activities, recreational pursuits, and educational pursuits. Advances in ICT are fostering globalisation, information sharing, and the expansion of cyberspace. The advantages of employing such technologies are enormous, and obvious wherever we look, telecommunication is here to stay, especially now, in the modern era of digital transformation, when people are more reliant on them and their derivatives. Additionally, these technologies have progressed into a variety of specialised specialist fields including connectivity, telecommunications equipment, telecommunications, internet access, etc.

Information on the use of communications technology for safety is presented and analysed critically here. From the responses to the survey questions, it is clear that the vast majority of people recognise and agree that communications play a significant part in ensuring safety, but the use of this knowledge to its full potential is yet to be attained. Supporting the finding of this study, Alzubai and Kalta (2016) posit that security detection and countermeasures are an alternative regulation method. Biometric technologies such as fingerprint readers, DNA sequencers, and voice recognition systems are only some of the many tools used for security detection. Accordingly to Johnny (2020), security operators can better analyse satellite photos for surveillance and criminal identification thanks to artificial intelligence (AI). In light of the findings shown in Table 2, it is clear that the Defence and Security course at NDA, Kaduna has no capacity for the necessary

communications instruments with which to deal with criminal activity. The Nigerian Defence Academy is known to use only tried and true information technology methods to provide the highest quality of service to its students. To achieve the academy's mission, suitable systems will be chosen and implemented based on their ability to enhance the availability of data, the quality of communication, and the efficiency of faculty and staff. Intuitive, user-friendly, and interoperable technologies are essential for reducing the need for manual data input and other forms of waste. The NDA has pledged to put in the required effort to maintain these systems, guaranteeing their safety, dependability, and precision with redundant hardware and software and comprehensive disaster recovery plans, but sadly have not reaped the benefits of telecommunication in fighting insecurity. Also Adigun et al (2020) noted that the rapid advancement of technology has opened up new vistas for communication, increased efficiency, and boosted growth, but it has also influenced a sea change in criminal behaviour. Some criminals exploit cutting-edge technology, making previously effective security measures obsolete. In Nigeria, this has led to a rise in security incidents, which the country's current security system is ill-equipped to address. As a result of technology's growing influence on the conduct of crime in Nigeria, cutting-edge tools must be used in the pursuit of security in keeping with international best practices.

5. CONCLUSION

The results demonstrated that the usage of telecommunications devices does not enhance security in NDA, as the cumulative mean value was 2.71, which is below the permissible mean value of 3.0. Telecom systems were not chosen and implemented at the Nigerian Defence Academy based on their efficiency in enhancing the availability and flow of information and the output of employees toward the academy's goals.

There is also the option of using detection and countermeasures to keep things safe. Numerous methods, such as biometric technology used for fingerprint analysis, DNA detection, and voice recognition, are used for security detection (Alzubai & Kalta, 2016). Artificial intelligence (AI) is being used by security personnel better to understand satellite photos for surveillance and criminal identification, as stated by Johnny (2020). The expense of countering security is high, the stress on the operator is high, and the potential for loss of life is high. Most anti-security tools of today are high-tech, pricey, and need a high level of technical expertise to use effectively. In light of the above, it is clear that technology is the driving force behind the struggle against security.

6. RECOMMENDATIONS

Given the significance of cutting-edge technology in the war on insecurity and the difficulties in implementing it effectively, the study makes the following suggestions:

- i. The Nigerian government's various security agencies should prioritise ICT education and training. Technical induction training for all newcomers to the Nigerian security service and mandatory computer literacy requirements would accomplish this goal. All members of the armed forces who are not proficient in the use of computers must get ICT training to arm themselves with the technical know-how essential to battle the rising tide of contemporary crime. This calls for the mobilisation of all Nigerian military training facilities.
- ii. Legislation mandating the long-term, cost-effective acquisition of crime-fighting equipment has to be officially promulgated by the Federal Government of Nigeria. To that end, the Nigerian security force would be supplied with the latest technological advances regularly.
- iii. The government should also provide the infrastructure, such as a reliable power source, that is essential to making the most of technological tools. The Nigerian government must invest in infrastructure, including electricity grids, internet connections, telecommunications and computer gear, optical fibre cables, and more, if the country's security agencies will efficiently use information and communication technologies.
- iv. The police and citizens of Nigeria need to shift their mindsets about using new technology. They must be shown all the wonderful possibilities and advantages of embracing contemporary technology. More effort should be made to educate the public about the importance of using ICT to report security incidents to law enforcement if the government is serious about embracing new technologies.
- v. The government should show greater dedication by passing enabling legislation to facilitate the long-term acquisition of cutting-edge tools for fighting crime in Nigeria.

vi. To reduce or remove manual data input and unnecessary steps, telecommunications systems should be user-friendly, well-organized, and interoperable. As technology is essential to fostering better communication and information distribution, NDA must dedicate the required communication resources to maintain these systems and guarantee their security, stability, and correctness, as well as provide for suitable backup and disaster recovery.

REFERENCES

- [1] Adigun, J. O., Raimi, L., & Mutiu, R. M. (2020). Fortification of Policing in Nigeria Using ICT Backbone for Strategic Competitive Advantage: Trends, Challenges, and Prospects. *Handbook of Research on IT Applications for Strategic Competitive Advantage and Decision Making*, 1-16.
- [2] Alzubaidi, A., & Kalita, J. (2016). Authentication of smartphone users using behavioural biometrics. *IEEE Communications Surveys & Tutorials*, 18(3), 1998-2026.
- [3] Bougie, R., & Sekaran, U. (2019). *Research methods for business: A skill building approach*.
- [4] John Wiley & Sons. Daly, S. (2003). Fight terrorism with intelligence, not might. *Christian Science Monitor*, 26.
- [5] Fatile, J. O., Adejuwon, D., & Bello, W. O. (2018). Community policing through the neighbourhood Watch A strategic security development in Lagos state, Nigeria. *Security and future of African states. Calabar: International Institute for Policy Review and Development Strategies*, 244-275.
- [6] Howell, A. (2018). Forget “militarization”: Race, disability and the “martial politics” of the police and the university. *International Feminist Journal of Politics*, 20(2), 117-136.
- [7] Nachmias, C. F., & Nachmias, D. (2015). *Research Methods in the Social Sciences*. (5th Ed.). London, UK: Holder Education.
- [8] Ogu, E. C., & Oyerinde, O. D. (2014). *ICT and national security in developing and underdeveloped countries the Good, the bad and the ugly: a case study of Nigeria’s cyberspace*. Nigeria.
- [9] Rahi, S. (2017). Research design and methods: A systematic review of research paradigms, sampling issues and instruments development. *International Journal of Economics & Management Sciences*, 6(2), 1-5.
- [10] Saunders, M.N.K., Lewis, P., & Thornhill, A., (2019). *Research Methods for Business Students Eight Edition. QualitativeMarket Research: An International Journal*.
- [11] White, T. L., & McBurney, D. H. (2022). *Research methods*. Cengage Learning. Nigeria.